

receives more rain, Egypt can expand its agricultural land outside of the delta.

Raised Mediterranean Sea level. The low elevation of the lands in the northern delta make them the most vulnerable in Egypt to inundation from rising sea levels. It is estimated that a 2-m rise in sea level would inundate about 50% of the ricelands and a 4-m rise would inundate almost all. Infrastructure to protect the delta is in place, but extensive renovations may be required to accommodate a rise in sea level, including salt water intrusion barricades across the Nile branches, a network of deep drains with pumps to discharge drainage water into the sea, and even construction of a seawall along the 250 km of the delta coast.

A more pressing problem may be reversing the hydrostatic pressure on soil salts. With the current sea level, the flooded ricefields provide a positive hydrostatic pressure to leach salts from the soil. If the sea level rises above the ricelands, the hydrostatic pressure would be reversed and the natural pressure would be for salts to move up in the soil profile. If this happens, rice may become a more important component in the crop rotation and have to be grown more frequently, increasing the water required to protect the land from salinity.

Cropping season. The subtropical climate, with full irrigation, supports an intensive fully double-cropped system, with distinct summer and winter growing seasons. Rice is planted in the spring, as the increasing mean temperature exceeds 20 °C, and is harvested in the fall, when the declining mean temperature returns to 20 °C (Fig. 1). Although the mean temperature is above 20 °C and maximum temperature approaches 35 °C, the mean night temperature is always below 20 °C. These cool temperatures delay maturity in rice by up to 30 d compared with tropical areas. The effect of these seasonal temperatures is a marked decline in yields because planting is delayed (Fig. 2). This is attributed to plants maturing with progressively cooler temperatures. Along with the decline in yield, a significant deterioration in grain quality occurs as the head rice yield declines and broken rice increases.

1. Average minimum and maximum temperatures at Sakha, Egypt.

2. Impact of date of sowing on GZ4120.

If a 5 °C uniform increase in temperature occurs, the following may happen.

- The potential growing season may increase by 10 d in both spring and fall.
- The warmer temperatures during maturity could reduce the rate of yield decline associated with late planting, thus providing higher and more stable average yields. Temperatures exceeding 40 °C, however, could cause sterility and grain shriveling.
- Fewer nights when the minimum temperature drops below 20 °C could reduce the maturity time of rice, allowing earlier planting of winter crops but not double-cropping rice.
- Higher temperatures may result in increased evapotranspiration and water requirements.

Rice production in Egypt could be very sensitive to global warming. While a

warmer climate may increase potential rice yields, there are risks and concerns about Egypt's water supply, inundation if sea level rises, and increased soil salinity. ■

Lipid peroxidation and superoxide dismutase activity in rice leaves as affected by ultraviolet-B radiation

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Enhanced UV-B radiation affects many processes in plants, such as growth, flowering, pigmentation, respiration, photosynthesis, and stomatal behavior. Recent experiments have demonstrated that UV-B treatment had significant effects on lipid peroxidation and superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity (Krizek et al 1993) in cucumber leaves.

No study had been conducted, however, on changes in lipid peroxidation and the enzymatic defense system of rice plants under UV-B treatment. The objectives of this study were to determine the effect of enhanced UV-A on SOD activity and lipid peroxidation in the rice plant and to characterize the role of SOD in modulating rice plant response to UV-B.

Seeds of IR74 and Naizersail rice cultivars were pregerminated at 30 °C for 24 h and then sown in 1-liter plastic pots containing 1.7 kg of soil fertilized with 0.4 N, 0.1 g P, and 0.3 g K. The plants were grown in a greenhouse for 10 d and then subjected to UV-B radiation in a temperature- and humidity-controlled phytotron (day/night temperature = 27/21 °C; RH = 70%). Photosynthetic photon flux at the top of the rice canopy under the UV-B lamps was about 940 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$ per/s. UV-B radiation was supplied by pre-aged UV-emitting fluorescent lamps that were enclosed in either presolarized 0.13-mm thick cellulose acetate (transmission down to 290 nm) for the UV-B treatment or 0.13-

mm thick clear polyester film (optically equivalent to Mylar D, absorbing almost all radiation below 320 nm) for the control treatment. The level of biologically effective UV-B radiation (UV-B_{BE}), when weighted according to the general plant-action spectrum and normalized to unity at 300 nm, was 13.0 kJ/m² per d. Control plants received no UV-B. The SOD activity was assayed by the method of Stewart and Bewley (1980). The level of lipid peroxidation in the tissue was measured as malondialdehyde (MDA, a product of lipid peroxidation) content, determined by the method of Heath and Packer (1968).

The MDA content in the leaves of both IR74 and Naizersail was increased after exposure to UV-B radiation. The percent increase of MDA in Naizersail was greater than that in IR74 (Fig. 1a and c). Initially, SOD activity based on protein content in the two cultivars was stimulated significantly by enhanced UV-B radiation (Fig. 1b and d). SOD activity started to decrease on the 20th day and the 15th day in IR74 and Naizersail.

respectively, under elevated UV-B radiation. The activity based on fresh weight had the same trend (data not shown).

Varietal differences in sensitivity to UV-B radiation, in terms of many growth and physiological parameters, have been reported (Dai et al 1992, He et al 1993). The present study shows that Naizersail, a UV-B-sensitive cultivar, had greater concentrations of MDA than IR74, which is less sensitive to UV-B. This indicates that more lipid peroxidation occurred in Naizersail upon UV-B irradiation which was consistent with the results obtained in cucumber (Kramer et al 1991). SOD activity in IR74 was not only much greater than that in Naizersail, but it also decreased later. This finding is different from the results in cucumber leaves, in which SOD activity decreased in leaf 1 but increased in leaf 3 (Krizek et al 1993). Although SOD activity in rice leaves increased under UV-B radiation, it might not be able to scavenge all the active oxygen induced by UV-B. This suggests that UV-B-induced cell injury was, at least partly, the result of decreased enzymatic defense ability.

The results of the present study show that genotypic variation in UV-B sensitivity may be because of differences in enzymatic defense ability to lipid oxidation activity and concentration of defense enzymes among genotypes. Further research is needed to determine if enhanced UV-A radiation stimulates active oxygen production in rice plants.

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